

Solute-Solvent Interactions in Multicomponent Electrolyte Solutions

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The viscosities of multicomponent electrolyte solutions in water, determined at 30°, have been analysed by means of Jones-Dole equation. The results are interpreted in terms of solute-solvent interaction by the magnitude of B-coefficient of the Jones-Dole equation. Positive B values have been found in all systems, suggesting the structure promoter nature, except in the case of H₂O+LiCl+KCl(C) system indicating no change in the structure breaking tendency of the KCl solutions.

THE study of solute-solvent interactions by means of molar volume^{1,2}, free energies of transfer³⁻⁵, conductance^{6,7} and viscosity⁸⁻¹¹ studies have received great importance among physical chemists. Literature reports many such studies with single component solutions in water, but investigations in multicomponent solutions involving mixed solvent are rather scanty. Only a few references on viscosity of mixtures of electrolytes in water are noticed in literature¹²⁻¹⁴. Recently Padova *et al.*⁵ determined the activity coefficients in the aqueous quaternary system NaCl-KCl-MgCl₂ from isopiestic measurements at 25°. The object of the present study is to investigate the solute-solvent interaction of some multicomponent electrolyte solutions involving 1:1 electrolytes in water, from viscosity studies. The concentrations selected were above 0.09 M as the main interest was to study at higher concentrations.

Experimental

Materials: Water needed for the preparation of various solutions was prepared by thrice redistilling distilled water over alkaline KMnO₄. The specific conductance of the water thus prepared was 1.3×10^{-6} ohm⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Potassium and sodium chlorides were of AnalaR grade and were used without further purification. Lithium chloride (B.D.H.) was purified by recrystallisation from water and dried for 24 hr at 130° in an oven. The electrolytes were kept over P₂O₅ in a vacuum desiccator before use.

Procedure: All solutions were made by weight and conversion of the molality into molarity was carried out by the usual expression¹⁵. The viscosity¹⁷ and density¹⁸ measurements were made by the methods described in our earlier publications. All the measurements were made in a thermostat having fluctuations in temperature of less than $\pm 0.05^\circ$. The standard deviations in the viscosity and density are ± 0.02 mp and ± 0.000011 g. cm⁻³, respectively. The measurements were made within a few hours of preparing the solutions.

Results and Discussion

The viscosity values of different multicomponent solutions in water at 30° are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—VISCOSITY OF MULTICOMPONENT SOLUTION IN WATER AT 30°

Molarity $C \times 10^3$ (mol. l ⁻¹)	Viscosity η_s (millipoise)
Solute : NaCl Solvent : 0.01 m KCl in water Viscosity (η_0) : 7.99 millipoise	
19.848	8.13
29.724	8.19
39.539	8.26
58.994	8.40
78.938	8.54
Solute : LiCl Solvent : 0.01 m KCl in water Viscosity (η_0) : 7.99 millipoise	
9.928	8.09
19.811	8.15
39.471	8.34
58.919	8.57
78.169	8.80
Solute : KCl Solvent : 0.01 m LiCl in water Viscosity (η_0) : 7.94 millipoise	
9.955	7.93
29.696	7.84
39.470	7.80
58.703	7.74
78.044	7.68
Solute : NaCl Solvent : 0.01 m LiCl in water Viscosity (η_0) : 7.94 millipoise	
19.931	8.08
29.800	8.17
39.579	8.29
59.194	8.49
78.630	8.60
Solute : KCl Solvent : 0.01 m NaCl in water Viscosity (η_0) : 8.05 millipoise	
9.933	7.94
19.803	7.93
29.612	7.92
39.379	7.93
58.801	7.95
77.986	8.01

(Table 1 Contd.)

Solute : LiCl	
Solvent : 0.01 m NaCl in water	
Viscosity (η_0) : 8.05 millipoise	
9.932	8.09
19.792	8.11
29.663	8.15
39.474	8.24
58.971	8.44
Solute : KCl	
Solvent : 0.01 m LiCl + 0.01 m NaCl in water	
Viscosity (η_0) : 7.98 millipoise	
9.954	7.94
19.859	7.98
29.633	7.94
39.471	7.94
58.908	7.98
78.114	7.92
Solute : NaCl	
Solvent : 0.01 m KCl + 0.01 m LiCl in water	
Viscosity (η_0) : 7.91 millipoise	
9.968	7.98
19.917	8.06
29.781	8.13
39.682	8.19
59.203	8.32
78.651	8.48
Solute : LiCl	
Solvent : 0.01 m NaCl + 0.01 m KCl in water	
Viscosity (η_0) : 7.73 millipoise	
19.857	7.90
29.706	7.98
39.519	8.08
58.968	8.32
78.287	8.56

linear plots of $(\eta_s/\eta_0 - 1)/C^{\frac{1}{2}}$ versus $C^{\frac{1}{2}}$. The values of A and B in different solutions are given in Table 2.

Table 2 shows that negative values of A have been obtained in all the multicomponent solutions. The negative values of A cannot be explained by Falkenhagen theory²⁰. However, when electrolytes are taken at higher concentration, A approaches zero and such situations are not uncommon²²⁻²⁵.

The +B parameter is noticed in the systems 1-5 indicating the structure making capacity of the varying electrolytes in the electrolyte of fixed concentration in water. However, in solvent system 6 i.e. LiCl + H₂O, KCl shows negative B coefficient, thereby indicating its structure breaking capacity as shown in pure water²², but KCl shows structure making capacity in other solvent systems. The reason may be obvious from the fact that Li⁺ ion is much smaller compared to K⁺ ion and is highly hydrated and potassium is unable to disturb the highly hydrated lithium structure and no change is observed in the character of KCl in LiCl + H₂O system. However, it disturbs the structure of aqueous NaCl and there is a possibility of association, and so the structure making tendency is observed in the presence of NaCl. Further, it is found to be more pronounced when studied in NaCl + H₂O system than in LiCl + NaCl + H₂O system, and the positive B values obtained for the electrolytes in multicomponent solutions behave as

TABLE 2—JONES-DOLE PARAMETERS FOR LiCl, NaCl AND KCl IN DIFFERENT MULTICOMPONENT SOLUTIONS AT 30°

Solvent system	LiCl		NaCl		KCl	
	A (mol ⁻¹ . cm ^{3/2})	B (mol ⁻¹ . cm ³)	A (mol ⁻¹ . cm ^{3/2})	B (mol ⁻¹ . cm ³)	A (mol ⁻¹ . cm ^{3/2})	B (mol ⁻¹ . cm ³)
1. 0.01 m NaCl + H ₂ O	-0.001 ± 0.001	+0.164 ± 0.0005	—	—	-0.057 ± 0.0005	+0.0547 ± 0.0002
2. 0.01 m KCl + H ₂ O	-0.0015 ± 0.0015	+0.122 ± 0.002	-0.001 ± 0.001	+0.090 ± 0.002	—	—
3. 0.01 m LiCl + 0.01 m NaCl + H ₂ O	—	—	—	—	-0.0165 ± 0.0005	+0.0120 ± 0.0005
4. 0.01 m LiCl + 0.01 m KCl + H ₂ O	—	—	-0.00075 ± 0.00075	+0.0924 ± 0.0005	—	—
5. 0.01 m NaCl + 0.01 m KCl + H ₂ O	-0.0005 ± 0.0005	+0.0163 ± 0.0001	—	—	—	—
6. 0.01 m LiCl + H ₂ O	—	—	-0.001 ± 0.001	+0.106 ± 0.003	-0.00025 ± 0.00025	-0.0420 ± 0.0002

The data was analysed with the help of Jones-Dole¹⁹ equation :

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = 1 + AC^{\frac{1}{2}} + BC \quad \dots (1)$$

where η_s = viscosity of solution, η_0 = viscosity of solvent, C = molar concentration of the solute, A and B = constants, characteristic of electrolyte.

The A coefficient represents the contribution from ion-ion interaction²⁰. The B parameter, which measures the structure making/breaking capacity²¹ of an electrolyte in solution, also contains a contribution from structural effects and is responsible for ion-solvent interaction in a solvent.

The values of parameters A and B of equation (1) are determined from the intercept and slope of

structure makers in the order LiCl > NaCl > KCl. The same order of association has been seen from the dissociation constant studies of these systems²⁶.

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